

Facilitating Business Success by Gaining Trust in Society

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Abstract

Nowadays trust is an essential intangible asset, a premise for growth and development of society at micro and macro levels. Trustworthy relations impose the vector of society's development. At the same time, trustworthy relations reflect the society's ripeness level and potential for prosperity. Trust reflects the quality of relationship between economic agents and defines the pace of sustainable development of the country. Trust affects the formation of people's relationships with customers, companies, investors, producers, managers and other stakeholders.

Establishing trustworthy relationships is a complex historical process. It has its own genesis, evolution sequences and life cycles. The history, norms, customs, traditions and culture create the collective memory over the centuries. This is the way, how the unique structure of relationship between the members of the society forms. A collective memory and collective consciousness determine the specificity of relationships between people wherever they are: in companies or other institutions.

As a post-Soviet country, the rate of trust in Georgia is low. It is a result of tough historical experience, constant threats and risks, betrayed expectations of people.

At the same time nepotism, protectionism, discredited judiciary system rooted in the country make economic and social relationships gloomy and uncertain. In such unhealthy conditions, mistrust is a kind of defense tool for society members, despite the fact that it (mistrust) makes economic processes more complicated and expensive.

The presented work is a quantitative study conducted in Georgia. Based on a survey data, the research investigates the influence of social trust on business success. The paper highlights the reasons for mistrust, defines the specifics of socio-economic relations in the country and explains how mistrust challenges companies' growth and success.

Key words: trust, trustworthy relations, history, collective memory, fail, risks, company, growth, society, mistrust.

Introduction

Trust is a fundamental concept of modern socio-economic and political life. At all stages of human history it remains persistently pressing issue as it defines the vector and the pace of social development. Being a powerful regulating and synchronizing tool of socio-economic relations, trust has been established throughout the whole history of humankind. Trust is generally defined as a confident or optimistic expectation, or as a feeling of security, which can be perceptual or attitudinal, concerning the behavior of others. This refers to the fact that the person who trusts feels safe, assured and comfortable about the prospect of depending on the person who is being trusted. The essence of trust can also be described through the contrary definition: mistrust, violation, delinquency, dishonesty, failure, betrayal, unrealized expectations.

The long process of human history is associated with the constructing of trustworthy relations, which united people into groups to achieve common goals. At the initial stages of development, trust was a mean of survival. Based on trust people united to be able to survive in tough conditions, overcome natural disasters, establish societies and states, protect territories, adopt laws, form rules and establish human rights. Trust allows humans to form communities, cooperate and even, at times, find solutions beyond plain self-interest. Trust affects how we form relationships with our family and friends, and why and how we develop business relationships or decide to buy products in the marketplace. (Möhlmann & Geissinger, 2018)

The 20th century globalization and industrialization went in line with the extension of the private sector and the companies' thriving productivity growth. The activities of the companies spread beyond the borders of local markets and they got inspired to gain the trust and the loyalty of customers around the world. Nowadays, there are over 333.34 million companies worldwide, 60,000 are multinational. They control 500,000 subsidiaries, which represent half of the international trade. The world production boom predetermined the permanent desire of companies to adapt production forces to new, advanced means of production. In pursuit of leadership in a competitive race, companies are constantly looking for unique ways to maximize current profits (Nino Zarnade; Tea Kasradze, 2020).

Long-term economic forecasts of global development predict a slowdown in global GDP growth. Between 2022-2030 average global potential GDP growth is expected to decline by roughly a third from the rate that prevailed in the first decade of the century - to 2.2% a year. For developing economies, the decline will be equally steep: from 6% a year between 2000 and 2010 to 4% a year over the remainder of this decade. These declines would be much steeper in the event of a global financial crisis or a recession (The World Bank Report, 2023).

In order to maximize profits, companies are in a persistent search of unique ways to conquer customers' loyalty, enter the new markets and improve the quality of goods and services. Obviously, companies with a good reputation (high rating, positive customer reviews) are more attractive to consumers and, therefore, have an advantage in competition. (Nino Zarnade; Tea Kasradze, 2020) In order to gain a competitive advantage, create a positive image, enhance the reputation and excel at customer service, companies spend large amounts of financial resources on marketing activities.

Literature Review - Building trustworthy relations –the key objective of modern companies

Trust is integral to the functioning of any society. Trust in each other, in our public institutions and in our leaders are all essential ingredients for social and economic progress, allowing people to cooperate with and express solidarity for one another. It allows public bodies to plan and execute policies and deliver services. Greater public trust has been found to improve compliance in regulations and tax collections, even respect for property rights. It also gives confidence to consumers and investors, crucial to creating jobs and the functioning of economies more broadly. Success in achieving each of the Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs)- from eliminations poverty (SDG1), to combatting climate change (SDG13), to building peaceful and inclusive societies (SDG16)- will depend on citizens' and business trust in public institutions and in each other (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2021)

Gaining the loyalty and the trust of consumers, suppliers and other business stakeholders has become the urgent task today. In fact, the entire production machine and all the mechanisms of the market economy focus on building trust-based relationships with consumers and gaining their loyalty. According to a new McKinsey report, when organizations invest in earning consumer trust, they will most likely see the highest top and bottom-line growth rates. According to the 2021 survey of 1,000 consumers concluded that more than 80% consider trust a decision factor in their buying decisions. According to the McKinsey research group, companies spend \$1 trillion on marketing globally. That is more than the total profits of the Fortune 500 and just a little less than the gross domestic product of Mexico. Annual marketing spending will reach \$4.7 trillion by 2025, which represents a growth of \$1.1 trillion from 2021 to 2025 (Duncan MacRae , 2022).

Trust is a liquid intangible asset, a platform for building trust-based relationships with customers. No trust equals no customers. The decision to place one's trust in another is seen as a deliberate and conscious strategy that can be used to maximize success, however defined (Roy J. Lewicki, Daniel J. McAllister and Robert J. Bies, 1998).

According to the Akeneo survey (a global leader company in Product Experience Management and Product Information Management), ten percent of consumers are willing to pay fifty percent more and eighty-two percent of consumers - thirty percent more for a company's product with which they have common values. Famous companies Amazon, Google, Sony, Netflix, Tesla, Visa, Band-Aid, Lysol, Clorox, Nike, Apple, Toyota, Chevrolet and many others are characterized by the highest rate of trust.

Modern companies try to build a special organizational culture to strengthen interconnections in the companies, as organizational culture is the connecting core that turns the crowd into a holistic organization. Moreover, the stronger the connections between the members of the group, the more transparent the values and rules in the organization are

formulated, the higher the degree of their acceptance by people, the greater the likelihood of high motivation of the staff, their productivity, and High Performance. The studies confirm that eighty-eight percent of the surveyed employees of American companies believe that a strong organizational culture is key to the success of the organization. Ninety-four percent of managers agree with this (Nino Zarnade; Tea Kasradze, 2020). Eighty-two percent of respondents to this survey believe that culture is a potential competitive advantage.

According to PwC's findings, when companies took action to gain trust, eighty-eight percent of customers would recommend them to others, ninety-one percent would think highly of them, eighty-three percent would defend them to others and sixty percent would even be more likely to share information about them on social media (Francesca Cassidy, 2022).

Trust as a key factor for companies' growth is getting more and more essential with time. The rapidly changing environment, nontransparent socio-economic and political situation in the world, the growth of population and the rising number of companies require searching new ways to attract customers.

Today companies' success is connected to its business biography and reputation, the satisfaction and the transparency of the relationship on the market, the shared history created with the consumers. In the end, these factors define consumers' behavior and decisions.

Consumers' satisfaction becomes a main objective of business. It is a chain lining up process among stakeholders. Constructing trustworthy, financially effective relations is a long-term work, which reflects in well-organized, synchronized actions of suppliers, distributors, financial and insurance organizations and other stakeholders. Therefore, trust here has an integral function.

Each part of the abovementioned complex production chain is a separate business process itself, driven by people and their ability to cooperate persistently, transparently and with the low transaction costs.

Therefore, in the conditions of the global market pressing issues and the high sensitivity of companies to external factors, the business prosperity and the efficiency of the companies correlate with the stability and empowerment of the supporting subsystems. The more structured, sustained and reliable the subsystems are, the more profitable and efficient the company appears. Building trustworthy relationships with business agents converts to high operational efficiency and profitability, customer and employee satisfaction, lower transaction costs.

It is worth to note, that it is almost impossible to imagine a company being able to be trusted by its customers if it's not trusted by its employees (McKensy and Company, 2021). The extent to how reliable and protected from uncertainty employees feel in a company depends their motivation for work, productivity and engagement. Obviously, satisfied and dedicated employees create healthy environment for the development and growth, provide stability and high productivity. Trust covers all business relations and makes them interdependent. For example, as a result of a survey conducted by the State Public Relations Services in the USA, it was determined that two-thirds of the respondents show more trust in companies that take care of their employees. Forty-four percent of respondents have more confidence in the products of companies that are active in solving social problems whereas fifty-two percent of them claim that an enhancement in product and service quality leads to an increase in customer trust.

Trust reduces risks and makes the process of planning and decision-making more reliable. It contributes to the establishment of partnership relations on the market and makes relations between partners more transparent and predictable. In the works Apotheosis of Trust, Luhmann points out that trust involves a telescoping of present and future. Trust allows for predicting future processes.

Establishing trustworthy relations at a workplace has become a new trend in the entire business society especially in the past century. For example, the Edelman Trust Barometer survey conducted in 2022 in developed countries, founded, that "Employees now see their workplace as a safe space for debate and turn to it as a primary source of community — before their neighbors and religious organizations". The study found that seventy-one percent of employees feel trusted by their CEO, seventy-eight percent of them trust their CEO, and ninety percent trust their manager. In today's world, trust in the workplace is a new company credo. "There is a new employer mandate: employers must leverage the powerful force of employees to restore societal trust from the inside out — from the workplace to the marketplace" (Edelman Trust Barometer , 2022).

It is important to note, that trust is reversible. This means, that the employees who believe that they are not trusted by their employers, do not trust them in return. According to Edelman's Trust Barometer, twenty-nine percent of employees who feel they are distrusted by their CEOs, do not have a high level of trust in their employers and managers either. However, trust in the company is very important for the employer, as no manager can detect every single failure of an employee to cooperate or every single performance that needs to be rewarded, he needs to be able to trust that his employees will act in a responsible manner based on a feeling of obligation to the organization, and that they would willingly defer to organizational authorities (Oliver Wendell Holme, 2013).

So, if it is proven, that the improvement of the company's performance and prosperity is directly related to the level of trust in relations within the company, what is the obstacle to move this direction? What are the prerequisites of transparent, reliable, trustworthy relations in companies and are there any links with social structures, society specifics in general? Why the level of transpersonal, social trust in developed countries is higher, than in developing ones?

Trust in Georgian Companies

Searching the answers to this question, we decided to analyze the experience of Georgia - the post- Soviet country, in which the past still has an influence the present. Our research aimed to find out the level of trust in Georgian companies and to expertise are there any links between the level of trust in companies and the level of trust in the society in general.

The research has been conducted by mixed methods, which provide both quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide more holistic understanding or the research question. Four hundred twenty people in total were interviewed and only employed people were asked to take part in the research. The questioner consisted from twenty-five multiple-choice questions. Employees both from the public and private companies took part in the study. We studied peoples' attitude to trust, their understandings and knowledge about trust. During the research, we were interested does trust influence workers' productivity. Is there interdependence between trust and the success of the company? Why has trust become so important nowadays? What is the reason for mistrust in the companies? Does mistrust in the companies correlate with the mistrust in the society? We were also interested what the reason for mistrust is. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative methodology has enabled us to identify existing challenges and develop relevant recommendations. According to the survey, respondents associate trust with such essence as hope, good expectations, respect and appreciation, empathy and understanding, support when needed.

Diagram 1 What is the essence of trust?

People strongly believe that trustworthy relations between employer and employees influence the success of the company, its performance and sustainable development. Ninety-two percent of respondents say trust between team members increase employees motivation, enhances their engagement in ongoing processes and strengthens companies' interconnections. More than eighty percent of employees admits that trustworthy relations between employees will have positive impact on their productivity and work efficiency.

Diagram 2 Trustworthy relations between employer and employees influence the success of the company

Nevertheless, the close observation shows, that fifty-three percent of respondents say they mostly do not trust their employers. Moreover, they think, that their employer doesn't know anything about employees and their work. Employers use their skills to maximize companies' profit. Both of them- employers and employees strictly follow the labor contract. Only thirty-four percent trust their employers and consider that both employers and employees strengthen each other. Diagram 3 Do you trust your employer?

Fifteen percent of employees are not sure that in difficult situations they can count on support of employer; seven percent of respondents are sure they will not have support; twenty- eight percent think that in hard times employers will firstly think of themselves. Summarizing the answers it can be admitted, that more than fifty percent of respondents (every second person) don't trust or trust their employer very conditionally and it dependence on situation.

Diagram 4 Employer will support and stay for me, if I am in difficult situation

The picture, which figures out from the research is about a lack of trust in the companies among team-members, deficit of faith in each other and unsustainability of predictions for even the closest future. It is worth to say, that the answers in the questioner were sometimes contradicting, very general and not clear, what, as we think, is a result of underestimating the role and the meaning of trust as an important welfare-driving concept in the society.

Moreover, mistrust has become a normal way of living and acting in Georgian society. The society, in which nepotism, lobbyism and protectionism at the workplace is a part of a daily routine, uses mistrust and control perception as a sword and a shield from the uncertainties and risks of failure. Perhaps this is the only right way of doing business in the society, where the legal framework and socio-economic platform for trust hasn't been created yet. Moving in an unclear environment the survival of each person depends on skills. Dealing under a permanent emergent danger pressure, people strengthen interconnections in small groups, tribes, friends, relatives; tend to separate from the external world to minimize risks of failure, tend to put a total control on all the processes concerning their interests. The perception of mistrust in return deepens nepotism, corruption and disseminates skepticism and suspiciousness in the society.

Therefore, the way team members collaborate and cohabitate in the companies is a reflection of the socio-cultural and historic processes of society's evolution. In general, a national culture largely determines the priorities of local companies and forms the nature of the organizational culture of companies. The history of the development of local companies is inextricably linked with the history of the development of economic relations in society, and, accordingly, with the culture of a particular society (Nino Zarnade; Tea Kasradze, 2020).

Trust in the Georgian Society

Let's look back at the past of Georgian society and try to find out the answers for mistrust in the history of the Georgian society.

In the work *Cultural Psychology: Exploring Culture and Mind in Diverse Communities* the author Robyn M. Homes explores how culture broadly connects to individuals acquire skills, values and abilities (Robin M. Holmes, 2020). The author suggests the view of people behavior as an outcome of their lives and experience during the evolution of the society.

The social psychology and behavior, social attitudes and relationships are raised from the history and evolution of each group. So does the trustworthy relations and mistrust. They both come from the objective reality and form specific culture of relations. Trust as a social category goes hand in hand with the development of society and has its own genesis, development trends and its own life cycle. Norms, rules, values, traditions, and history form a certain structure of relations between group members. They are transported from generation to generation and form collective memory, collective consciousness. The importance and benefits of trust highlight the need to understand how trust develops and the ways national culture affects the trust-building process. Although trust may form in a variety of ways, whether and how trust is established depending upon the societal norms and values that guide people's behavior and beliefs (Geert Hofstede, 1980).

Talking about Georgia, we are describing the part of the Soviet Union and at the same time a generation of persistently betrayed people who were chronically immersed in ideological propaganda and left to sink by the state. These people believe that there can be no trust in public institutions and only the strongest survive.

We lean towards the view that the low extent of trust in Georgian companies is a part of a more general problem. The mistrust in the companies derives from the mistrust in the society.

The difficult experience gained during the existence of the Soviet Union left an indelible mark on the consciousness of people. Here we are not talking about the isolated cases of violation of human rights or unfair treatment of a person. We are talking about a system, in which discrimination and violation was the norm. This was a system, which solved its problems with the force at the expense of vulnerable groups.

Let us look back to only some facts from the newest history of Georgia and a former USSR:

- ✓ 1917-1918 - the companies' owners went bankrupt in one day as a result of the nationalization of lands, enterprises, banks, and insurance companies declared by the government establishment;
- ✓ 1922-1923- the full confiscation of the property and the valuables from the churches;
- ✓ 1929-1934 – the collectivization in villages, de-kulakization and confiscation of their property;
- ✓ 1922-1956 – forcing people for taking "state loans" in the amount of 2-3 months' salary. The loss of the population then amounted to 3.5 billion rubles;
- ✓ In 1947 - the financial reform in a form of confiscation. The same thing happened during the Russia-Ukraine war, when the Russian Federation blocked people's income in banks and still does not allow them to dispose their savings;
- ✓ 1957- soviet establishment announced the freezing of payments on government loans for 25 years. It was stated that the freeze was made "at the request of the workers".

This is the overview of just a first half of the 20th century but the same processes continue until today. The mistrust in the society becomes absolutely clear and understandable. It turns to the sword and the shield for protecting own interests. At the same time mistrust causes skepticism and suspiciousness, instigate to nepotism and protectionism, breeds polarization and contributes to a corruption (Kasradze Tea; Zarnadze Nino, 2018).

The reliability and the transparency of the political and economic systems has always been challenging for Georgia. Corruption and nepotism, protectionism, lobbyism and shadow economy are still a normal form of living in the country.

Even though Georgia started developing towards European value system in the late 90-s of the 20th century and the conducted reforms brought positive results in some directions, the situation is still complicated. Suffice it to say only thirty-four percent of the respondents surveyed in our research agreed with the statement "people can be trusted". Only twenty four percent of respondents mostly trust the government officials and consider their policy transparent, taken decisions clear and acceptable.

Diagram 5 Do you trust authorities in your country?

Meanwhile, thirty-seven percent says that the members of Georgian ruling party serve their own interests and are not concerned with people’s needs.

Thirty-seven percent of the respondents do not know anything about the reforms and nineteen percent says that the conducted reforms are mostly beneficial for authorities’ self-prosperity.

Diagram 6 Do you agree that reforms conducted in the country are beneficial for you and your family.

As a legal system has a fundamental power in societal construction, our next investigation deserve special consideration. Bearing in mind, that a legal system is a framework of rules, procedures and institutions that ensure the supremacy of law in the community and provide the security of individuals, it must be transparent, trustworthy and sustained. The most developed countries such as United Kingdom, Germany, Denmark, Switzerland, United States, Norway, Canada, etc. have mature legal systems, which means the ripeness of the legal system to be objective and (fair-minded) produce fairness. The mature societies are not those with unbreakable rules, but those, where law protects the human rights. Looking back to our research, we have found out, that only seventeen percent of respondents trust and forty-two present declare mistrust to the Georgian legal system.

According to the Business Association of Georgian (BAG) Index and Institute for Economic Research, forty-one percent of Georgian companies have a low level of trust in the Georgian judicial system, while nine percent have none at all. Only eighteen percent of the surveyed business indicated high level of trust in Georgian courts.

.Diagram 7 Do you trust the legal system in Georgia?

A similar example can be given in the field of education or healthcare systems, where the most of the respondents are express skepticism. Only fourteen percent of respondents express trust to national healthcare system, while eighty-six percent directly or indirectly express doubts.

Diagram 8 Do you trust the healthcare system in your country?

As it comes out from the survey, there is a low level of trust in government bodies, state institutions in the country. Here mistrust has become a kind of defense mechanism, where skepticism is important and doubts- necessary for survival. The mistrust sowed in people is becomes obvious in all the areas of their lives, in relations between team-members, employer-employees, counterparts of the production process etc.

It is interesting and worth attention that, almost eighty-five percent of surveyed respondents believe that none of their Georgia’s geographical neighbors (Russia, Turkey, Azerbaijan, Armenia) can be trusted. All of them have their own interest, which does not correspond to the interest of Georgia, it is necessary to conduct a diplomatic policy with them and strengthen defense mechanisms. In fact, seven out of ten people not only mistrust the states of the bordering areas, but have negative expectations. They urge to mobilize resources and reflect attacks for self-defense when needed.

Diagram 9 Whom from the geographical neighbors of Georgia can be trusted?

It is clear, that the trust in the society in general and in some groups in particular can be increased only with the help of efficient legal system and sustained social institutions. Trustworthy relations need transparent environment in which human rights are protected and privileged upon ineffectiveness and failures of the system.

Summary and Recommendations

Constructing efficient relations in groups is a challenging process, in which sustainability and consistency provide outcomes. This is a process, which covers all groups of society and influences different forms of relations from interpersonal relations in a workplace to interconnections among government and civil society.

One can put much effort in creating values and rules within the company. Still, people who work in the companies come from a particular society and their historical and cultural issues should be taken into consideration. The lesson we learnt from the past is, that though trust is not easy to quantify. It can be built, won, lost or betrayed. And evidently, that the costs of restoring, reanimating trust is much higher than the costs for building it.

Facilitating business success, increasing production forces is linked to creating trustworthy environment in society in general. It stimulates the competitiveness of the companies, increases consumption, and motivates consumer to buy and employee to work. The trustworthy relations have a positive impact not only on companies but also on the economy of the country. Worth to say that the meaning of trust is especially essential for financial institutions, insurance and investment companies, because they create a platform for socio-economic development. The positive effect of improving relations in society will have a positive impact on the work performance of the companies. Improving the global environment for business functioning will create new opportunities, accelerate the pace of development, and create a favorable environment for the development of economic relations at the micro and macro levels. Trust as an intangible resource reflects the level of development of social and economic relations. It should be noted that mistrust breeds insecurity and skepticism. It makes person indecisive and suspicious. Suspiciousness causes hypercontrol and aggression. As a result for the companies, mistrust becomes mutual and cooperation less cost effective.

Constructing efficient legal system, creating institutions which protect rights and interests of the consumers, increasing transparency of the actions of the stakeholders can become a real power for facilitating business success and economic growth in the country. The main priorities of development should be justice, responsibility, transparency, equality of opportunities and the rule of law. Based on these principles, trusting relationships create a special culture of interaction between members of society.

In conditions of low trust the social responsibility of business, the engagement of companies in social projects, the support of society in the areas of education, medicine, recreation and other social activities becomes extremely important (Kasradze Tea; Machkhashvili Sopio, 2022). This is the right way to improve reputation and value of the company and increase trust. Business consolidation around solving social problems will have a positive impact on the companies themselves and make socio-economic environment more trustworthy.

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Short Biography

Short Biography –Nino Zarnadze Doctor of Economics, Associate Professor, Business and Technology Faculty, Caucasus International University. Research interests: business success, development, trust, cooperation, educational leadership, society and evolution.

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